

Long-term monitoring of the optical performance of the primary mirrors at the Coihueco and Loma Amarilla sites of the Pierre Auger Observatory

Reflectance Measurements of Mirror Segments (CO Bay 5 and LA Bay 3)

This repository contains the evaluated measurement data used for the analysis and figures presented in the publication.

Overview

The datasets provide reflectance characteristics for eight right edge mirror segments located in Bay 5 at the Coihueco (CO) station and eight right edge mirror segments located in Bay 3 at the Loma Amarilla (LA) sites.

These measurements are important for understanding the optical performance and aging of the Fluorescence Detector mirrors.

Database Content

The processed data is organized in the following archive files:

- `data_uscan.zip` — Specular and diffuse reflectance components at 670 nm,
- `data_spectralrefl.zip` — Hemispherical reflectance vs. wavelength.

Dataset Descriptions

1. `data_uscan`

- **Description:** This directory contains data files with specular and diffuse reflectance values and their uncertainties for the selected mirror segments specifically at the 670 nm wavelength. Data were taken by a uScan device.
- **File Format:** .csv
- **Data Details:** Each file corresponds to a selected mirror.

2. `data_spectralrefl`

- **Description:** This directory contains data files with hemispherical reflectance values and their uncertainties as a function of wavelength for only one selected mirror segment. Data were taken using a setup with an Avantes spectrometer.
- **File Format:** .txt
- **Data Details:** Each file corresponds to a specific mirror and a specific measurement timestamp (`year_months`).

Relation to Publication

The data stored here serves as the direct source for the plots presented in the manuscript.

Contact and Information

For further details regarding the measurement methodology or data evaluation, please contact paper coordinator Pavel Horvath, pavel.horvath@upol.cz.